

Offline Learning: Lived Experience of Students in Remote Areas During the Covid-19 Pandemic

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Abstract

Offline learning is a learning modality that refers to modular learning, mobile learning, distance learning, self-learning and independent learning in the context of the study. The lived experiences of the participants in offline learning was investigated using descriptive phenomenological by Husserl. Purposive sampling was used to select the ten participants in the study. Unstructured in-depth interviews were guided by the main question: can you please share with me your stories about your offline learning experiences? (Mahimu ba nga imu ko'ng saysayan kabahin sa offline learning?). By applying Colaizzi's method, the were seven clustered themes generated: technological competence; transfer of knowledge; communication issues; learning strategy; undesirable behavior; quality assessment; and physio-emotional well-being.

In general, participants have experienced tremendous struggle in offline learning because of limited access to internet connection, have less technological competence, and have not received timely feedback. These experiences triggered the participants to cultivate undesirable academic practices devaluing academic integrity. On the other hand, participants have learned to develop different learning strategies in offline learning. Yet, grades became a major concern because participants felt either underserved or overserved with it. Significantly, these offline learning experiences have caused emotional and physical exhaustion among the participants. It is then recommended that learning activities and assessments should lead students to more independent thinking. Student-centered learning should be prioritized by developing engaging offline communities and designing lessons that leverage technology tools and instructional models that actively engage students in each part of the learning process.

Introduction

Offline learning is a learning modality that refers to modular learning, mobile learning, distance learning, self-learning and independent learning. Offline learning is observed when students engaged learning through using modules either printed or electronic or digital copy. In this context, the role of technology is only to let students download the learning materials and submit their outputs. In addition to, offline learning suggests independent learning since students are learning without the guidance of an instructor and allows students to take responsibility of their learning.

As noted, students living in remote areas which is 20 kilometers and beyond away from the school and can only be accessed by motorcycles where internet connection is very low to no connection at all opted to choose offline learning. Most of the students are using Facebook for communication processes only and few are using devices for learning processes (Barrera et al., 2020). Thus, printed materials' distribution is an option in studying at offline learning education (Martin et al., 2020). In the state universities, students who are living nearby the university are asked to get their modules at the campus while those living in remote areas are instructed to go to the designated area where modules are brought and distributed to them.

With the presence of COVID-19 virus, college students are advised to stay and learn at the comfort of their home. Due to health crisis, colleges and universities decided to adopt offline learning (Bozkurt et al., 2020). Hence, offline learning addresses the needs of the learners when health security is at risk. Through this, instructors can safely provide instruction to students without requiring them to be physically present in order to learn. In this context, college students are left alone to learn concepts and work for their learning outputs and projects. Philippine Daily Inquirer (2020) reported that most of the educators preferred to have offline learning where self-directed instruction is applied.

In the Philippines, according to CHED CMO No. 7 s. 2020, offline learning education is taking place when these components are utilized in the conduct of teaching learning process: in terms of technology, it is in the forms of reproduced modules, audiotapes, videotapes, CDs, storage devices, learning packets, television,

radio, broadcasting networks, learning management system (portable/cloud); in terms of educational materials, it is printed or electronic modules, video, audio, podcasts, webcasts, Open Educational Resources (OERs) in storage devices, OERs, learning materials. The outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic caused enormous disturbances in people's lives as well as in educational institutions. Students' learning as well as learning modality were severely disrupted as a result of the worldwide education institution shutdown. The coronavirus outbreak has had an impact on the worldwide education system. During the health crisis, educational institutions are working to ensure that learning is not hindered. In lieu of in-person learning, CHED advised HEIs to utilize their best judgment in utilizing available flexible learning and other nontraditional modes of delivery. Faculty discretion in higher education institutions must be reasonable, transparent, and outcome-based verified. Flexible learning, which is a learner-centered technique firmly focused on student needs, aims to provide learners with the greatest flexibility in terms of learning material, scheduling, access, and creative evaluation, employing both digital and non-digital technologies. It is an approach where students can choose the pace, place, and mode of delivery of their lessons. Offline learning is a flexible learning mode that does not require internet connectivity and instead relies on printed modules or digital forms such as video and audio stored on storage devices to ensure that students who do not have access to the internet can cope and complete their studies while remaining safe.

Further, offline learning is a method of instruction in which the learner and the teacher are physically isolated. According to Owusu and Amoakogene (2020), this method of education aims to provide learning opportunity to all students, regardless of their circumstances. Further, Joaquin et al. (2020) added that learning innovations must be based on a better knowledge of offline learning education and sensitive to changing circumstances. But Toquero (2020) stressed that challenges arise in migrating from a physical classroom to offline learning. Further, French (2015) argued that offline learning can cause fragmentation and obtuseness in the academic experience, as well as weakening learning outcomes and posing epistemological, systemic, and pedagogical issues. Another concern as reported by Lalu (2020), Filipino students who were able to enroll have to suffer an unhealthy learning environment in offline learning education because some of them are experiencing domestic violence which is an add-on to submitting requirements and beating deadlines. By statistics more than 30% of 15-year-old learners do not have a private spot to study at home, according to PISA (2020), in Indonesia, the Philippines, and Thailand. Ramos (2020), as cited in Inquirer.NET, said that students were digitally divided during global health crisis. Based on the survey conducted in the Philippines, intermittent internet connection was experienced by 98% of the faculty and 94% of the students thus the need to change to offline learning.

Being new to this modality, this paper captures the experiences of the college students who are currently engaged in offline learning. According to the study, offline learning necessitates more desire to complete activities, stay interested, and improve. Students procrastinate in offline learning since they are learning at home and think they will have more time to complete the work. Also, due to sudden change, students find it difficult to adapt to an offline learning environment that resulted to low academic interest. In many cases, students find difficulty in managing their time in offline learning since students are more engaged in household chores while doing academic tasks.

This paper analyzes the challenges revolving around this modality and how college students address these. Moreover, this study helps Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) to see the situations that the students are facing in offline learning and later craft a more responsive-meaningful offline learning experience.

Literature Review

Offline learning education helps students to cater to the demands of a wider range of student groups while also giving them more freedom and choice about how they manage their studies (French, 2015). The use of offline learning education classrooms will enable students to continue their education even if the pandemic strikes. Offline learning education has the benefit of allowing for leniency in emergency situations, enabling training experiences to continue (Toquero, 2020). Offline instruction eliminates the need for students to commute to universities and schools. It's better to ensure that students are paying attention to the course materials for offline learning. Any student finds it easier to keep their offline learning experience and skills (cpduk.co.uk, 2020). Offline learning is a form of education in which students are not restricted by learning opportunities or time restrictions. During the pandemic, the majority of colleges begin their studies through offline learning (Ince, 2020)

Schools can create new distribution methods, which may include TV shows (if a collaboration with media is possible), podcasts, radio interviews, and multimedia or paper-based learning packages. However, the unusual conditions in which any likely alternate mode of education might be continued throughout the pandemic should be noted (Reimers & Schleider, 2020).

Academic institutions have used remote mobile learning (offline learning) as a result of the Philippines' slowest and least stable internet connection, according to Internet Quality Index 2020. In this type of learning, instructors are sending their instructions and learning materials in the Messenger --- an application

mostly used by the college students. This is convenient especially for those living in remote areas since they can easily access the application even if internet connection is poor. In this way, education has continued even during the COVID-19 pandemic. Sung et al. (2016) predicted that mobile learning holds a lot of promise for enabling more creative instructional methods. In addition to subject content learning, this learning would surely benefit in the development of communication, problem-solving, imagination, and other high-level skills among learners.

Several studies on mobile learning (offline learning) have been undertaken in order to better explain how mobile devices are used in educational environments, and this means that mobile learning is beneficial to both learners and teachers (Aubusson et al., 2009). Mobile learning refers to learning that takes place on a mobile device and has a number of advantages (Crompton et al., 2018). For starters, this teaching method may be used anywhere, at any time, and the learning process is not limited to a specific area (Corbeil & Valdes-Corbeil, 2007). It also encourages teachers to customize teaching and learners to self-regulate their learning (Sha et al., 2012). Naciri et al. (2020) concluded that mobile learning (offline learning) is an unescapable alternative during COVID-19.

One of the features of offline learning is using a teaching module. This is thought to develop strategic reasoning and problem-solving capabilities while still increasing constructive learning. For both professors and students, utilizing an offline learning creates a more flexible learning atmosphere (Cheng & Abu Bakar, 2020). Modular learning allows learners more freedom and choice in managing their studies while also catering to the demands of more varied student classes (French, 2015). Modular learning (offline) is more effective in the teaching learning process than standard teaching methods (face-to-face learning). This modular method allows students to study at their own pace. It's a free self-learning method in which pupils are motivated and their interest is piqued by direct encouragement and input during practice sessions. In terms of completing tasks on the spot, the modular method increases the chance of student engagement in the classroom. As a result, pupils have the freedom to study in their own way (Sadiq & Samir, 2014). However, Alvarez (2021) cited some issues encountered in the modular distance approach, such as communication failure, such as instructions or student confusion on modules, limited teacher guidance, students behaving badly toward teachers, complaints about not understanding the module, and all of this leading to student misbehavior and failure to pass worksheets on time. In addition, students face problems such as a lack of a steady internet connection, a suitable gadget or device, an unsuitable learning management system or platform, and the absence of regulations and procedures for flexible learning (Tuga et. al., 2021).

Scholars have laid bricks of evidence suggested that student performance in offline learning based on student demographic characteristics was the same as those engaged in online learning (Huh et al., 2010). When analyzing student performance based on student completion rates of materials, Olson (2002) found insufficient data to imply that offline instruction is a factor influencing a student's completion of their education. Surprisingly, Trawick et al. (2010) discovered that students performed worse in online classes than in offline classes. When compared to traditional learning, offline learning instruction is as effective as traditional learning in terms of student mastery and can be even more effective in terms of student capabilities (face-to-face learning). More research is needed, however, into students' perceptions of and satisfaction with offline learning education, as well as its cost-effectiveness, usability or affordability improvements, and any unexpected or bad consequences (Car, 2019). Rasmussen et al. (2014) revealed that students found significantly higher improvements in offline learning compared to traditional learning in tests measuring knowledge increases (face-to-face learning). It was also discovered that eLearning resulted in much higher skill increases. There were no differences in opinions or preferences for eLearning over traditional learning in general. In the study of Yen et al. (2018), students found offline learning as effective and were satisfied. Also, it was concluded that quality student learning can occur in offline learning. In comparison to modular learning, learners learn better when they utilize social media platforms for learning since there is continual contact and sharing of ideas within the class, which is not present in the modular learning setup. Furthermore, people are more happy with the learning quality since their participation improves learning reception and retention (Avila & Cabrera, 2020).

Research Question

The study aims to understand the essence of offline learning to the participants as this is new to them. Further, the premise of the study is to provide meaning of the lived experiences of the participants in offline learning. Generally, this seeks to describe the offline learning experiences of the participants living in remote areas. What are the experiences of the college students living in remote areas in offline learning?

Method

The phenomenological method developed by Edmund Husserl was used in this study. Phenomenological research was utilized to figure out the underlying structure of some social phenomenon's common essences (Worthington, 2013), and focuses on the essence or structure of an experience (Merriam, 2002). The goal of the phenomenological technique is to unearth the true experience of the thing being studied (Turunen et al., 1994). In this study, offline learning in remote areas was being studied. The aim of this study was to understand the essence of being a student drastically exposed to offline learning, as this greatly helps the academe to see the situation. Specifically, this study underscored the instruction, learning materials and assessment processes as experienced by the college students in offline learning. Within this perspective, this study utilized a descriptive phenomenology or Eidetic following the works of Husserl. The researchers follow the four (4) steps in descriptive phenomenological Eidetic design: bracketing; intuiting; analyzing; and describing. First, in bracketing, the researchers identify preconceived beliefs and opinions about the phenomenon. This is known as epoche. Researchers' expectations and assumptions are bracketed prior to doing analysis. Accordingly, each researcher wrote their own experiences with regards to the delivery of instructions, construction of learning materials and the process of assessing students' learning in offline learning modality. Moreover, their preconceptions in relation to their emotions, values and knowledge were described especially on the gathering, interpretation and presentation of data. Second, in intuiting, the researchers see the phenomenon as free from prejudice and biases. Third, in analyzing, the researchers start to get significant statements lifted from the interviews, followed by crafting formulated meanings, then to writing themes and finally to come up with theme clusters. Finally, in describing, an exhaustive description is formulated based from the clustered themes. Since the study is descriptive phenomenology, Colaizzi's method will be applied. Familiarization, selecting significant statements, constructing meanings, grouping themes, generating an extensive description, producing the basic structure, and requesting verification of the fundamental structure are the seven processes in Colaizzi's method (Morrow et al., 2015).

This study was conducted in the Western part of Cebu, Philippines. Due to its geographical location, this region is having poor internet connection. Thus, most students enrolled in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) are adopting offline learning. Given the situation, proximity of their residence, accessibility of transportation and availability of internet connection becomes a learning barrier. Experiences of students particularly in terms of instruction, learning materials and assessment processes might be distinct from the rest of the students. Within this notion, the researchers are inclined to understand more the experiences of students living in remote areas considering the mentioned situation.

Purposive sampling was used in this investigation. Purposive sampling is a type of nonprobability sampling that is utilized when the goal of the study isn't to provide data that can be used to make broad generalizations about the whole population (Etikan et al., 2016) and the study is to describe only a phenomenon and to (Albuquerque et al., 2014). In this study, the researchers select participants Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) who meet the inclusion criteria. In this study, participants were above 18 years old, enrolled in academic year 2020-2021, engaged in offline learning and are residing in remote areas regardless of their gender and taken degree programs. A total of 10 participants were included in the study.

Moreover, participants are receiving instructional modules either in printed copies by getting it from the their campuses by schedule or by downloading electronic copies sent through either in Facebook messenger, Facebook group page via private message or email. Within this context, participants are submitting their outputs by taking pictures or screenshots and are sent using Facebook messenger.

The tool that was used in this study were interview questions made by the researchers to elicit the essence of the experiences of the participants. These interview questions revolved around the meaning of offline learning experiences. Technically, the researchers adopted an unstructured interview to the participants. Participants were asked in English but is translated in Bisaya, in case that the participants find it hard to understand the questions. Mainly, they were asked with, can you please share with me your stories about your offline learning experiences? (*Mahimu ba nga imu ko'ng saysayan kabahin sa offline learning?*). Prompts and probe questions come along the way as the researchers engage themselves with the participants during the interview. Also, the researchers collected the demographic profile of the participants as these were important to describe them.

The gathering of data was done by interviewing the first participant of the study. Following Colaizzi's method, the gathered interviews was transcribed. The researchers started writing exhaustive descriptions after clustered themes were generated. When exhaustive description was done, the researchers went back to the participants and asked them to validate the result. After the analysis, the researchers presented the findings followed by the discussion.

Results

Theme Cluster: Technological Competence

Teaching, learning, curriculum, and assessment are all covered by technological competency. Knowledge of computers, tablets, interactive whiteboards, and cellphones, as well as how to use them, is referred to as technological knowledge (Gurbuz & Karanfil, 2021). In this study, “Technological Competence” is expressed in the following themes: technology is needed in accomplishing tasks in offline learning and internet connection plays a vital role in offline learning. Having limited knowledge on technology and how to use them limit the productivity of the students in meeting and submitting their tasks in offline learning. Through the help of internet connectivity and gadgets, students are asked to do task such as videos and submit it online though the modality of the instruction is offline learning. Yet, this scenario becomes a challenge on the part of the students.

The experience of having difficulty with using gadget is narrated by Participant 3:

I can send pictures but I find it really difficult to do a video presentation.

Even if the students have gadgets, their next concern is when they are asked to create videos as their tasks in offline learning. Participant 1 expressed his frustration:

I don't know how to use a laptop and I don't know how to do a video presentation.

Apart of not being knowledgeable enough to use gadgets and manipulate software, this situation was even made difficult by the location of the students to look for signal as expressed by Participant 7:

I have to climb mountains just to search for internet connectivity signal.

Adding to the burden of the students is the internet connectivity. Participant 3 feel frustrated whenever they submit videos:

There is a signal but the connection is unstable. It is very slow.

Participant 9 added:

I struggle most in sending vides because I have to wait until the dawn of 1 AM or 2 AM just to be able to send videos. I was very frustrated. In fact, I sent it for four times back when the weather is not fine.

On the other hand, Participant 2 has verbalized the importance of gadget and internet connectivity in offline learning:

I resorted to search possible ideas over the web. I'm allowed to use mobile phones or laptop using interne connection.

Participant 1 believes that having a gadget like laptop can help him do better in offline learning:

I need to buy laptop because I find it useful in offline learning.

The necessity of internet connection in offline learning is stressed happily further by Participant 3:

Internet connection. I have to install wifi connection... hahaha)

Theme Cluster: Transfer of Knowledge

Transfer of Knowledge is a process in which two agents exchange explicit or tacit knowledge in which one actor receives and uses the knowledge offered by the other (Krylova et al., 2016). In this study “Transfer of Knowledge” is expressed in the following themes: following instructions is difficult in offline learning, tasks are too challenging and offline learning is not effective. Offline learning enables the students to be more dependent on the teachers and the chances of discovering new things among themselves are also limited.

In offline learning, students experienced difficulty especially in accomplishing the tasks since they are not confident whether or not they have acquired the knowledge, skills and attitudes expected in a particular learning outcomes. These experiences are expressed by these participants:

Participant 1: I find instructions confusing and vague.

Participant 2: I find modular instruction not easy.

Participant 4: I find modular instruction hard and confusing.

Participant 7: I find modular instruction hard.

Also, three participants are disappointed because their instructors do not cannot understand the situation that they are facing. Participants really find offline learning difficult because apart from instructors are not around, resources and references are limited in reference to the module being given to them. Because of this limitation, participants are getting emotional and plead to their instructors not give more burden but instead be more considerate:

Participant 1: I suggest that my instructors should tailor-fit the projects based on the available resources of their students so as not to put pressure while in modular instruction.

Participant 8: Enough time should be afforded to finish the task.

Participant 9: Lessen the number of activities given to the students.

One significant aspect that Participant 2 experienced is the pressure coming from their parents telling them to stop for offline learning. They felt that offline learning is not effective as their parents keep on asking them to work for they believed that they won't learn at all by simply reading the modules all by themselves:

I am pressured by my parents to stop my studies and work instead. I am encouraged by my parents to stop for they believe modular instruction is useless.

Participants 8 exclaimed in a high note that offline learning is not effective at all:

Offline learning is not effective at all.

In fact, Participant 1 is very doubtful about his capability in relation to his degree program. He is cynical about his future career because of being exposed to offline learning:

I feel I am not equipped to graduate.

Theme Cluster: Communication Issues

Issues with communication can arise in any situation or social relationship. Individuals have a tendency to misunderstand or misinterpret others, which can lead to disagreements or friction in personal, platonic, or professional relationships. In some instances, conflicts may arise, and these conflicts can make communication even more challenging (Enke & Borchers, 2019). In this study, “communication issues” is expressed in the theme: communication becomes a challenge in offline learning. In offline learning, students are barred from approaching their instructor and instructors are also unresponsive to students' questions. In the case of offline learning, having these becomes a challenge for the students.

The experience of being restricted to approach their instructor in offline learning is described by Participants:

Participant 2: I cannot message directly some of my instructors. Like, I wanted to get answers right away. I am reluctant to approach my instructors

Participant 9: I am hesitant to approach my instructors.

Participant 5: I cannot easily communicate with my instructors due to poor internet connectivity.

Participant 7: The instructor was unresponsive to my queries.

Participant 4: When I communicate with my teachers with regards to my concerns, they are not responsive.

Participant 1 also added:

Instructors should check their students from time to time.

Theme Cluster: Learning Strategy

A learning strategy is a person's method of organizing and employing a certain set of skills in order to acquire content or complete other tasks more effectively and efficiently in academic and non-academic environments (Vernon et al., 2020). In this study, “Learning Strategy” is translated into this theme: offline learning permeates learning strategy. In offline learning, students are left alone to do their tasks found in the modules. This experience led them to device ways and look for strategy that they can use to allow them acquire the competency that are expected of them. Further, the learning strategy is detailed in the following formulated meanings: peer tutoring is restricted in offline learning, students are asking one another in answering tasks in offline learning, research is required in offline learning, self-learning is demonstrated in offline learning, and resourcefulness of the students is tested in offline learning.

One particular strategy that is not possible to offline learning is group study. Due to pandemic, students are not allowed to gather in one place. In fact, the longingness to have do a group study and peer tutoring are exclaimed by the Participants:

Participant 2: It feels good to see my classmates in a group study.

Participant 1: I collaborate with my classmates.

Because instructors cannot answer them right away, Participant 8 and 3 prefer to ask their classmates:

Participant 8: I prefer to ask my classmates.

Participant 3: I find way to be at my classmate's house.

Students are looking ways to communicate and help each other in the tasks in offline learning as expressed by these participants:

Participant 6: I communicate in our group chat, about the tasks. We are sharing our ideas about that certain topic and task.

Participant 2: I ask my classmate to type it for me and I just have to ask my classmates about other the tasks.

Participants claimed that they do research whenever that they get internet connection to understand the topics found in the modules:

Participant 4: I read and do advance research.

Participant 2: Through research gyud siya, pag-answer ug pagkat-on (I do research, to answer and learn).

Moreover, self-learning is shown by Participant 7 as he expressed that he relies on himself by kept on reading and later interpret what he read:

I just read, I interpret what I read on the module.

But Participant 9 finds his way to strategize by managing his time against the task by a checklist:

I do checklist, this should be done.

Theme Cluster: Undesirable Behavior

Inappropriate student behaviors have become a global concern in higher education (Linda & Nancy, 2004), making it a difficult and inevitable duty for both new and seasoned teachers. In reality, dealing with these undesired behaviors consumes a significant amount of time for teachers and has a negative impact on teaching and education. This does have an impact on the educational process's quality (Adem & James, 2015). In this study, "Undesirable Behavior" is expressed in the following themes: procrastinating and cheating is an opportunity in offline learning. Undesirable behaviors are unavoidable in offline learning, where students are allowed to employ self-learning modules in print or digital format/electronic copy. Since this is self-paced learning, students are highly procrastinating and cheating.

One undesirable behavior manifested by Participant 2 is when he said:

I procrastinate when doing modular tasks.

Being lazy to do offline learning tasks is worsened by the quality of learning material and poor learning management. This situation led to cheating among the students as shared by these participants:

Participant 5: I get bored whenever the print of the module is not clear and resort in copying my classmates' answers.

Participant 8: I am more inclined to do the tasks with deadlines than those that do not have one resulting to procrastination.

Participant 1 is unmotivated to study and because he has no one to ask for, he often procrastinates doing offline learning tasks. He emphasized that due to the low quality of the copy of the printed modules, it would make them feel demotivated to answer and would lead them to copy from their classmates' answer:

I feel uneasy being exposed with offline learning to the point that I lost interest to answer the tasks.

However, participants find their way to cope with the offline learning activities and to accomplish the tasks. Because of the lack of resources such as internet connection and gadgets and their environment at home, participants resorted to procrastination and later cheating. They have suggested the following to improve the offline learning experience:

Participant 1: I suggest that the university should provide learning devices that students can use to comfortably learn while in modular instruction.

Participant 7: I suggest that the university will provide laptop to the students.

Theme Cluster: Quality Assessment

In the educational process, good assessment design is critical. An assessment activity that is well-designed and articulated creates clear expectations for pupils. Students should be able to self-monitor, rehearse, practice, and receive feedback as part of the job (Theobald et al., 2019). It also has an impact on what a student learns, how he or she learns, and how much he or she learns. By assisting students in gaining a comprehensive understanding of their subjects and developing their capacity to judge their own and others' work, quality assessment design fosters lifelong learning practices. In this study, "quality assessment" is expressed in the following themes: Generosity in giving grades and grades do not equate competence. Quality assessment in the context of offline learning is greatly shaped based on the different observations and encounters of the students in this type of learning modality.

Grades do not reflect the actual competency as perceived by the students in offline learning which was shared by Participant 1:

I think that I don't deserve the grades that are given by some of my instructors against the efforts that I have exerted).

This was also supported with the experience of Participant 7 in his observation in terms of the grades that they have received:

My grade did not match the effort I exerted in answering the modular tasks.

In offline learning, other observations in terms of grade manipulation are also common as exposed by Participant 4:

Our grades were released even if our outputs are not yet checked by the instructor.

Participant 6 also stated that in his experience, grades are determined by the instructor's interaction:

My grades are low on subjects where the instructor interact less.

Participant 5 also mentioned that, based on his observations and personal experience, grades are determined by the students' efforts in offline learning:

Based on my efforts, I am satisfied by the grades given by my instructors.

While some participants are very concerned about the grades they have received in offline learning, as Participant 8 has revealed, some are not concerned about their scores in offline learning.

I don't mind the grades I have received from my instructors.

Theme Cluster: Physio-emotional Well-being

Both our mental and physical health have a role in our total well-being. This aspect pertains to one's physio-emotional well-being. Physio-emotional well-being is demonstrated by the fact that injuries and other bodily ailments have a significant impact on our emotions. Because our emotions have an impact on our physical health, this direct interaction is co-dependent. (Stoddard, 2019). In this study, one's "Physio-emotional Well-being" as a theme cluster is demonstrated by the theme: Offline learning is stressful.

The following statement by these participants express his difficulty in offline learning:

Participant 2: I'm trying to adjust to the online submission mechanism).

Participant 3: I strive hard to answer my offline learning tasks.

Aside from trying to be accustomed to the modality, three participants 2 and 9, and 6, respectively, expressed how offline learning has affected both their mental and physical health.

Participant 2: Mastress ka ba kun unsay pillion nimo (I feel stressed and emotional between continuing modular instruction or taking the advice of my parents to stop).

Participant 9: mukalit rakog hilak nga mura gaey mapuno na (I cry because I feel exhausted).

Participant 6: Lisod jud ang kanang magsoft copy miss kay kanang sakit kay sa mata (Reading e-modules affects my eyes).

Despite these stresses expressed, Participant 9 also articulated how he was able to cope with these strains:

I find ways to destress whenever I am exhausted with my modular tasks... (I prefer answering my modules when I am calm.

Exhaustive Description

The lived experience of the college students residing in the remote areas is experiencing hardship in navigating to tasks that require technological knowledge and skills. Due to inaccessibility to internet connectivity and limited technological competence, participants experienced problems in accomplishing and submitting their academic tasks. Also, their residence made it difficult to connect online where ample resources could have been accessed by them. This posits a contributory factor that limits the participants to become productive in offline learning. Another lived experience that participants had in offline learning is the acquisition of knowledge. In offline learning, participants felt not confident and were doubtful of their knowledge because they were simply given learning modules and left all alone to read, understand, perform and eventually answer these modules. Participants have experienced trouble following instruction due to the words, terminologies and construction of sentences used in the printed learning modules. This vagueness of instruction hampers them to comprehend the tasks and even more of the lessons. Because of these experiences, participants felt disappointed with regards to their experiences in offline learning, not to mention the misfit of tasks expected of them in a particular year level and course.

However, the experiences above were supposedly addressed if only college instructors were available for consultation. Communication between participants and their instructor is a one possible mean to help them cope with the lessons and gain meaningful offline learning experiences. Yet, as experienced by the college students in offline learning, they hardly get response from their instructors when they posed some clarificatory messages pertaining to the lessons and tasks in offline learning. Sadly, college students observed their college instructors unresponsive in offline learning. As a result, participants have devised and strategized ways just to cope with the lessons and tasks expected of them. This lived experience in offline learning of the college students allowed them to create different learning strategies which could be taken as one good outcome of offline learning. Apparently, the downside of offline learning as experienced of the college students is the increase of cheating incidents and procrastination to do the tasks. Because participants have greater freedom and time when and where to answer tasks found in the modules, they can easily ask for answers from their classmates who have accessed internet connectivity while other were putting aside their academic tasks. These were the undesirable practices among the college students experienced in offline learning. In addition, participants felt that the kind of grades they received in offline learning did not match with their effort and more so did not speak of about their actual knowledge and skills. There was a big gap between the grades and actual competencies as acquired by the participants. Grades were either very high or very low. Participants claimed that assessment is jeopardized in offline learning.

These experiences of the participants in offline learning have affected their physical and emotional beings. They expressed that they did not know how to do the tasks because they only have little understanding

about the lesson. Participants experienced stress and exhaustion brought by offline learning which resulted in them almost quitting schooling.

Discussion

When students understand the principles that structure, guide, and explain content and skills, they can more successfully transfer their knowledge. In offline learning, it allows students and teachers to stay connected and engaged with the information while working from their homes (Ray, 2020). Participants are provided with printed learning materials. Offline learning, on the other hand, was expected to add to the students' obstacles, as it was a modality that participants in remote places found problematic. Students can perform, according to Kober (2015), when they use their knowledge in a related context, such as a different class or assignment, or when they apply their information in an unrelated environment, such as field excursions, social engagement, or professional performance. Kober's finding is not observable as experienced by the participants because offline learning limits them to explore other areas that can test their acquisition of knowledge. On the other hand, offline learning helps the learners develop new strategies to cope with the different challenges brought by this type of learning modality. Participants employ a variety of learning tactics to achieve the same goal: academic success despite the tough environment. Participants stated that performing group study, which included visiting to their classmates' homes despite the risk, asking help, and cooperating with their classmates, had taught them and acquired new approaches. These new learning strategies are both beneficial and detrimental to academic success because these help them to become academically successful and at the same time prone them to academic dishonesty (Neroni et. al, 2019). It should be noted that while offline learning has been successful in providing access to individuals in a variety of situations, educators are increasingly recognizing the need to address quality issues as a major concern because offline learning differs significantly from the traditional classroom.

The 21st century has opened our doors to technology and has become an indispensable aspect of this totality of development. Technology has huge potential to enhance academic development in line with its analysis and its focus on practicality, specificity and continuity (Udoye and Onukafor, 2021). As participants navigate to offline learning, they are confronted with numerous tasks that ask them to use technological tools like creating videos and many more. Since participants were not exposed to these tasks, they found it very difficult to accomplish. Teachers should be able to use information and communication technology (ICT) effectively in order to live, learn, and work productively in an increasingly complex and information-rich world. It should be emphasized that teachers are the people who play the most crucial role in assisting pupils in acquiring important technological abilities (Castillo et al., 2016). In offline learning, however, instructors were not present to help them, making it more difficult for the participants to do the tasks. Indeed, technology can be a practical tool, hence, technological competence is a required basic skill in offline learning.

Many institutions have recently reported extensive cheating in online exams, and the problem has become so pervasive that it has even been covered by the media (Bilen & Matros, 2021). Similarly, in offline learning modality in the Philippines, examinations took place online by using Google forms. Participants were asked to take the assessment online and were given ample time to answer, especially those living in the remote areas where they still have to travel from their residence to a place where they have an internet connection. Moreover, cheating is rampant as experienced by the participants in offline learning. By engaging in academic dishonesty, this undermines the parameters of offline learning. Academic dishonesty can lower the quality of a student's learning experience, as well as the validity and trustworthiness of an online class's assessment (Costley, 2019).

Another issue to consider in offline learning is the communication problems that plague any communication process. Due to the physical distance between participants, poor technology skills, difficulty using media, the need for more human engagement, time constraints and restrictions, and a lack of expertise with distance education, communication issues are more prevalent in distant education (Berge, 2013). Because of these issues, establishing an offline learning process and developing good communication between participants and instructors is difficult. The lack of technology and instructors' lack of response exacerbated the communication gap. For a successful offline learning, an open communication was highlighted by the participants. Therefore, all strategies of learning communication and instruction should not reflect the barriers limitations (Simonson et. al., 2019). Due to sudden changes in the educational system, as well as the mode of instruction, participants find it difficult to adjust to offline learning thus affecting the physio-emotional well-being of students. Stress has been one of the regression analysis demonstrated by students with average academic performance that had increased vulnerability to emotional distress (Hassan, et.al 2022). As experienced by the participants, offline learning has become one of the stressors encountered.

Regardless of learning modalities, learning has always been the goal of educational programs (Abramovich, 2016). In this context, learning assessment is paramount in tertiary education for it is used in the educational field to know what are the priority needs that should be addressed. By definition, grades are numbers that show how good someone's work or performance is (Cambridge Dictionary). Oftentimes, college students are concerned with having higher grades as these suggest higher mastery of their expected

competencies. But as experienced by the participants, they were worried even if their grades were high. Participants pointed out that their earned grades did not reflect their true abilities as there were no learning encounters between them and their instructors. According to Menendez et al. (2019), students need ongoing and regular training to be able to apply theoretically or practically to recognize the problems of a topic, the knowledge obtained, and the students' triumphs. Participants, unfortunately, have never received instruction that assisted them in gaining knowledge and abilities that might lead to higher marks.

Conclusion

In general, participants have experienced tremendous struggle in offline learning for they have limited access to internet connection due to their geographical location, have less technological competence which is a prerequisite requirement to do most of the tasks found in the module, and have received minimal to no response from their instructors when concerns were raised. These experiences have triggered the participants to cultivate undesirable academic practices devaluing academic integrity. On the other hand, participants have learned to develop different learning strategies to be more productive in offline learning. Yet, grades became a major concern because participants felt either underserved or overserved with it. Significantly, these offline learning experiences have caused emotional and physical exhaustion among the participants.

Recommendations

Amidst the current COVID-19 crisis, many schools are reaching their learning community through remote, offline, or hybrid options. This shift to remote learning can be especially daunting for educators as we continue to scramble to best serve students and families yet equitable access to the resources and infrastructure needed to support students is not always available despite the progress that has been made in many places. Many of the learners do not have access to a device, stable internet connectivity, or, in some cases, stable electricity. Therefore, it is recommended that class activities and assessments should lead students to more independent thinking. A variety of academic strategies may also be stretched to address different issues brought by offline learning modality. Providing a clear sense of direction for intended learning can greatly help students in coping. Finally, just because a learning modality has abruptly switched to an offline setup does not indicate that students should be consigned to the role of passive information receivers. Instead, student-centered learning should be prioritized through creating engaging offline communities and designing classes that use digital tools and instructional models to actively engage students in all aspects of the learning process.

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References

- Abramovich, S. (2016). Understanding digital badges in higher education through assessment. *On the Horizon*.
- Albuquerque, U. P., de Lucena, R. F. P., & Neto, E. M. D. F. L. (2014). Selection of research participants. In *Methods and techniques in ethnobiology and ethnoecology* (pp. 1-13). Humana Press, New York, NY.
- Alvarez, M.Y. (2021). Issues and Concerns of Teachers in Mindanao State University – Sulu Towards Modular Distance Learning Approach: An Analysis. *Indonesian Community Empowerment Journal Vol 1 Issue 2*.
- Aubusson, P., Schuck, S., & Burden, K. (2009). Mobile learning for teacher professional learning: benefits, obstacles and issues. *ALT-J*, 17(3), 233-247.
- Avila, E.C. & Cabrera, H.I. (2020). The Use of Facebook Group in Distance Learning During the Time of COVID-19 Pandemic. *Scientific Journal in Paleontology and Egyptology. PJAEE*, 17 (6)
- Barrera, K. I. B., Jaminal, B. D., & Arcilla Jr, F. E. Readiness for Flexible Learning amidst COVID 19 Pandemic of Saint Michael College of Caraga, Philippines.
- Berge, Z. L. (2013). Barriers to communication in distance education. *Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education*, 14(1), 374-388.
- Bilen, E., & Matros, A. (2021). Online cheating amid COVID-19. *Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization*, 182, 196-211.
- Castillo, J. G. D., Herrera, P. J. C., Carrillo, J. A. O., & McCalman, D. G. (2016). Raising the technological competence of high school science and mathematics teachers of Mexico through delivery of an online program. *International Journal of Technology, Policy and Management*, 16(2), 163-180.
- Corbeil, J. R., & Valdes-Corbeil, M. E. (2007). Are you ready for mobile learning?. *Educause Quarterly*, 30(2), 51.
- Costley, J. (2019). Student perceptions of academic dishonesty at a cyber-university in South Korea. *Journal of Academic Ethics*, 17(2), 205-217.
- Crompton, H., & Burke, D. (2018). The use of mobile learning in higher education: A systematic review. *Computers & Education*, 123, 53-64.

- Detwiler, J.E. (2008). Comparing student performance in online and blended sections of a GIS programming class. *Transactions in GIS*, 12 (1), 131-144.
- Douglas W. Stoddard MD, E. and Douglas W. Stoddard MD, E., 2022. *The Hidden Emotional Benefits of Physiotherapy - Sports Medicine Clinic | SEMI*. [online] Sports Medicine Clinic | SEMI. Available at: <<https://www.semisportmed.com/the-hidden-emotional-benefits-of-physiotherapy/>> [Accessed 10 March 2022].
- Esquire Philippines. (2020, August 20). So, Yeah, the Philippines Has Expensive Turtle Internet, According to a New Study. *Tech*. <https://www.esquiremag.ph/culture/tech/philippines-internet-a00203-20200820>
- Etikan, I., Musa, S. A., & Alkassim, R. S. (2016). Comparison of convenience sampling and purposive sampling. *American journal of theoretical and applied statistics*, 5(1), 1-4.
- French, S. (2015). The benefits and challenges of modular higher education curricula. *Issues and ideas of paper*.
- Gürbüz, O. C. A. K., & Karanfil, B. (2021). Teachers' Perceptions of Their Technological Competence in Learning and Teaching Process. *Malaysian Online Journal of Educational Technology*, 9(4), 14-30.
- Hassan, S.-N., Algahtani, F. D., Atteya, M. R., Almishaal, A. A., Ahmed, A. A., Obeidat, S. T., Kamel, R. M., & Mohamed, R. F. (2021). The Impact of Extended E-Learning on Emotional Well-Being of Students during the COVID-19 Pandemic in Saudi Arabia. *Children*, 9(1), 13.
- Huh, S., Jin, J.J., Lee, K.J., and Yoo, S. (2010). Differential effects of student characteristics on performance: Online vis-à-vis offline accounting courses. *Academy of Education Leadership Journal*, 4.
- İnce, E. Y., Kabul, A., & Diler, İ. (2020). Distance education in higher education in the COVID-19 pandemic process: A case of Isparta Applied Sciences University. *Distance Education*, 4(4).
- Inquirer Philippines. (2020). Will distance learning work in PH?. Retrieved 18 November 2020, from <https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/1315763/will-distance-learning-work-in-ph>.
- Kristine Rasmussen, et.al. Offline eLearning for undergraduates in health professions: A systematic review of the impact on knowledge, skills, attitudes and satisfaction June 4, 2014 <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4073241/>
- Krylova, K. O., Vera, D., & Crossan, M. (2016). Knowledge transfer in knowledge-intensive organizations: the crucial role of improvisation in transferring and protecting knowledge. *Journal of Knowledge Management*.
- Lalu, G., 2020. *Why Push For Classes When Pandemic Affects Students' Mental Health? – CEGP To Deped, Ched*. [online] INQUIRER.net. Available at: <<https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/1323764/cegp-asks-deped-ched-why-push-classes-when-pandemic-affects-students-mental-health>> [Accessed 18 November 2020].
- Linda, B., & Nancy, S. (2004). Combating Classroom Misconduct (Incivility) with Bills of Rights. Submitted for publication in the Proceedings of the 4th Conference of the International Consortium for Educational Development, Ottawa, Ontario, Canada, June 21-23/2012.
- Lorainne Tudor Car. *Offline Digital Education for Medical Students: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis by the Digital Health Education Collaboration*. January 19, 2019. <https://www.jmir.org/2019/3/e13165/>
- Martin, K., Cupples, A., & Taherzadeh, S. (2020). Learning advanced engineering online: from distance delivery to online learning of finite element analysis. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 45(3), 457-472.
- Menéndez, I. Y. C., Napa, M. A. C., Moreira, M. L. M., & Zambrano, G. G. V. (2019). The importance of formative assessment in the learning teaching process. *International journal of social sciences and humanities*, 3(2), 238-249.
- Merriam, S. B. (2002). Introduction to qualitative research. *Qualitative research in practice: Examples for discussion and analysis*, 1(1), 1-17.
- Morrow, R., Rodriguez, A., & King, N. (2015). Colaizzi's descriptive phenomenological method. *The psychologist*, 28(8), 643-644.
- Naciri, A., Baba, M. A., Achbani, A., & Kharbach, A. (2020). Mobile learning in Higher education: Unavoidable alternative during COVID-19. *Aquademia*, 4(1), ep20016.
- Neroni, J., Meijs, C., Gijsselaers, H. J., Kirschner, P. A., & de Groot, R. H. (2019). Learning strategies and academic performance in distance education. *Learning and Individual Differences*, 73, 1-7
- Olson, D. A (2002). Comparison of online and lecture methods for delivering the CS 1 course. *Journal of Computer Sciences in Colleges*, 18 (2, Dec).
- Priluck, R. (2004). Web-assisted courses for business education: An examination of two sections of Principles of Marketing. *Journal of Marketing Education*, 26 (2), 161-173.
- Ramos, M. (2020). Educators step up for new revolution. Retrieved 18 November 2020, from <https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/1298852/educators-step-up-for-new-revolution>
- Ray, S., & Srivastava, S. (2020). Virtualization of science education: a lesson from the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Proteins and Proteomics*, 11(2), 77-80.
- Reimers, F. M., & Schleicher, A. (2020). A framework to guide an education response to the COVID-19 Pandemic of 2020. *OECD*. Retrieved April, 14, 2020.

- Sadiq, S. and Zamir, S., 2014. Effectiveness of Modular Approach in Teaching at University Level. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 5(17), p.108.
- Sha, L., Looi, C. K., Chen, W., & Zhang, B. H. (2012). Understanding mobile learning from the perspective of self-regulated learning. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 28(4), 366-378.
- Simonson, M., Zvacek, S. M., & Smaldino, S. (2019). Teaching and learning at a distance: Foundations of distance education 7th edition.
- Theobald, R. J., Goldhaber, D. D., Gratz, T. M., & Holden, K. L. (2019). Career and technical education, inclusion, and postsecondary outcomes for students with learning disabilities. *Journal of Learning Disabilities*, 52(2), 109-119.
- Toquero, C. M. (2020). Challenges and Opportunities for Higher Education Amid the COVID-19 Pandemic: The Philippine Context. *Pedagogical Research*, 5(4).
- Trawick, M.W., Lile, S.E. and Howsen, R.M. (2010). Predicting performance for online students: Is it better to be home alone? *Journal of Applied Economics and Policy*, 29 (Spring), 34-46.
- Tuga, B.J, Jocson, J.V., & Mabunga, R.A. (2021). The Impact of COVID-19 on a Philippine University: Challenges and responses towards a new normal in education. *AsTEN Journal of Teacher Education*.
- Turunen, H., Perälä, M. L., & Meriläinen, P. (1994). Modification of Colaizzi's phenomenological method; a study concerning quality care. *Hoitotiede*, 6(1), 8-15.
- Udoye, N., Onukafor, & Uchechukwu, M. (2021). Knowledge - Use of Technology and Teachers' Professional Development as Correlates of Successful Intelligence among Students with Physio - Emotional Disability. *IJSR*, 1-2.
- Vernon, D. S., Schumaker, J. B., & Deshler, D. D. (2020). The social and academic effects of cooperative LEARN strategy instruction in inclusive elementary classes. *Learning Disability Quarterly*, 0731948720944164.
- Worthington, M. (2013). Differences between phenomenological research and a basic qualitative research design. *Retrieved from*, 1149861.
- Yen, S. C., Lo, Y., Lee, A., & Enriquez, J. (2018). Learning online, offline, and in-between: comparing student academic outcomes and course satisfaction in face-to-face, online, and blended teaching modalities. *Education and Information Technologies*, 23(5), 2141-2153.

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